

Analysing similarities and differences between corpora

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Abstract

The notion of comparable corpora rests on our ability to assess the difference between corpora which are claimed to be comparable, but this activity is still art rather than proper science. Here I will discuss attempts at approximating the content of corpora collected from the Web using various methods, also in comparison to traditional corpora, such as the BNC. The procedure for estimating the corpus composition is based on selecting keywords, followed by hard clustering or by building topic models. This can apply to corpora within the same language, e.g., the BNC against various crawled Internet corpora, as well as to corpora in different languages, e.g., webpages collected using the same procedure for English and Russian. I will also discuss the differences in using hard clustering vs topic models.

1. Introduction

The British National Corpus (BNC) has been collected in the beginning of the 1990s using various written and spoken sources from the 1970s-1980s. It aims at representing modern English, but in many respects it is outdated and it does not cover many domains. The web is huge, it is easy to collect data from it either by using search engine queries (Baroni and Bernardini, 2004; Sharoff, 2006) or crawling respective websites (Joho and Sanderson, 2004). However, once we have a corpus, we still do not know its composition, e.g., the proportion of webpages for medical doctors and patients in the corpus of (Baroni and Bernardini, 2004), or to what extent the BNC is similar to a web corpus.

The problem of not knowing the content gets another dimension when we use comparable corpora, i.e., two corpora which are claimed to be similar in one aspect or the other. It is possible that comparable corpora are collected in their own ways and are drawn from different distributions, e.g., from different website or for different languages. For example, within the TTC project (Blancafort et al., 2010) our aim is to explore the possibility of mining terminological resources from specialised comparable corpora. For this task, we used parallel seeds to collect corpora on comparable topics by retrieving webpages returned in response to queries containing identical or nearly identical terms in several languages (below shown for English and Russian):

fossil fuel	ископаемое топливо
power station	электростанция
hydroelectricity	гидроэнергетика
photovoltaics	фотоэлектричество

However, the crucial question is: do we get comparable pages by sending comparable queries? One approach to comparing corpora across languages is by translating the features obtained from documents, usually such features are keywords (Adafre and de Rijke, 2006). However, translations listed in dictionaries are not always suitable in a given context. Also for many language pairs we lack reliable resources.

In this study I analyse ways of comparing the composition of different corpora using unsupervised methods for keyword selection and corpus classification.

2. Methodology

2.1. Corpora used for analysis

The BNC classifies its documents using a complex classification scheme (Lee, 2001), which includes such categories as

- domains (eight labels in total: natsci, appsci, socsci, belief, imaginative, leisure, business, world affairs);
- genre (seventy labels in total, W.advert, W.newsp.brdsheet.national.arts, etc)
- information about the audience, author, publication medium, etc.

In spite of the complexity of the classification system, it does not cover many substantial differences between the BNC texts, e.g., a text from socsci can be from the subdomain of linguistics or history, the domain of world affairs covers both local British and international politics. The composition of the BNC can be compared to ukWac and itWac (Baroni et al., 2009), large corpora crawled from the .uk and .it domains to represent respectively British English and Italian (with subsequent language filtering). Another task is to compare the composition of specialised corpora collected using comparable seeds (Table 1).

2.2. Keyword selection

The procedure for selecting the keywords per each document was based on the Log-likelihood (LL) score (Rayson et al., 2004). Like the commonly used tf*idf score the procedure is language-independent, but unlike tf*idf it takes into account the relative frequency of a term in a document against the reference corpus as well as the absolute number of its occurrences as the evidence of its statistical significance. The LL-score also allows setting a straightforward threshold using the value of 10.83 ($p = 0.001$) or 15.13 ($p = 0.0001$), for the justification see (Rayson et al., 2004). An example of keywords is shown below:¹

¹Extracted from the ukWac page <http://www.comp.leeds.ac.uk/biosystems/neuroscience.shtml>

Table 1: Corpora used in this study (sizes given in tokens and documents)

Corpus	BNC	ukWac	itWac	EN-Energy	RU-Energy	ZH-Energy
Tokens	111246939	2119891296	179512658	7505765	7766462	12431752
Documents	4054	2541926	175646	5762	5126	3287

LL-score	N	Keyword
126.07	7	Womble
101.47	9	neural
91.26	6	elegans
62.55	13	model
47.22	6	simulation
46.47	10	network
39.59	3	locomotion
36.66	3	biologically
26.71	3	constrain
21.95	3	nervous
21.78	3	cognitive
	...	

They are all useful for describing this individual webpage, but some of them (*Womble*, *elegans*) are too specific for the purpose of clustering webpages of a general-purpose corpus: *Womble* is a keyword for only 22 pages in ukWac, so it is less useful for finding its clusters. Also a corpus of the size of ukWac generates 89,394 unique keywords for clustering its 2,541,926 documents, causing dimensionality problems. Restricting the keyword lexicon down to the most common words² limits the ability to select pages with specific topics, so a simple approach used in this study was to reduce the amount of keywords down to the 10,000 words most often selected as keywords in the entire corpus. The use of the complete set of keywords tested on the BNC was marginally detrimental to the results. The clusters remained the same with the exception of lumping the clusters of investment with environment and medicine with biology and splitting the clusters of education and politics.

2.3. Clustering methods

For unsupervised detection of domains two scenarios were used, hard clustering and generation of topic models. Because of the need to cluster a fairly large number of webpages, the repeated bisection (RB) algorithm was used in Cluto (Zhao and Karypis, 2004), as it is quite efficient and tends to produce clearly interpretable results, cf also a study in (Steinbach et al., 2000). A cluster is treated as a subcorpus and described in terms of its keywords against the entire the corpus.

Generation of topic models is based on Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), which estimates the distribution of probabilities of keywords belonging to different topics (as in traditional clustering, the number of topics is set at the beginning of the experiment, but not the allocation of topics to documents), while the distribution is derived from the distribution of hidden variables (like in Hidden Markov models). This setup helps in generalising inherent similarities between the keywords, see (Blei et al., 2003). For each topic we get the degree of its association with documents and keywords. The advantage of topic models in compar-

ison to RB clustering is that each document gets a degree of its association with each topic, so that it can belong to several topics at once. However, this does not allow us to estimate the partitioning of the entire corpus into a set of clusters in order to compare their relative sizes.

It is known from prior experience that there are more topics in the BNC than the set indicated in its classification scheme, so more than eight clusters need to be used. In all experiments with general-purpose corpora I used 20 clusters. This number helped in producing interpretable models covering a diverse set of topics, while a larger number of clusters makes the comparison task inherently difficult. As discussed in (Chang et al., 2009), there is no correlation between human perception of the consistency of clusters and automatic measures (such as perplexity or I_2), so it is difficult to estimate the right amount of clusters automatically, while in the context of this study there was no scope for a proper human evaluation of the quality of each clustering solution for each corpus. CLUTO (Zhao and Karypis, 2004) uses I_2 as the standard objective function, which maximises the cosine similarity between each node and the centroid of the clusters it belongs to. I_2 on the BNC grew slowly when the number of clusters varied from 10 to 27 (reflecting the reduced size of each cluster), so no definite estimate towards the desired number of clusters can be made:

N	I_2	N	I_2	N	I_2
10	1.38	16	1.49	22	1.57
11	1.40	17	1.50	23	1.58
12	1.42	18	1.52	24	1.59
13	1.44	19	1.53	25	1.60
14	1.46	20	1.55	26	1.61
15	1.47	21	1.56	27	1.62

3. Results

Even though corpus analysis via clustering is more important for web-derived corpora, because we do not know their exact composition, it makes sense to evaluate our methods on a corpus we know better, such as the BNC (Section 3.1.). Then, in Section 3.2. I will compare ukWac and itWac, two general-purpose Internet corpora, to the BNC. Finally, I will present a study of specialised comparable corpora across different languages (Section 3.3.).

3.1. Clusters in the BNC

Table 2 lists the clusters and topic models with their keywords. The clusters produced by Cluto are numbered according to their internal consistency (the smallest number for the greatest consistency). Also, at the bottom of the list of clusters I indicate the most frequent genre categories from the BNC associated with this genre. In case the genre is not informative (*W.misc*), the most common domain

²As done, for example, in (Kilgariff, 2001).

Table 2: Clusters (above) and topic models (below) in the BNC

0	3.3%	Inc, Corp, software, user, Unix, system, lifespan, IBM, module, application, version, package, file
1	1.5%	studio, video-tape, speaker, voice, read, over, report, say, yesterday, male, police, Oxford, Swindon
2	1.7%	pollution, environmental, conservation, nuclear, emission, waste, energy, forest, ozonosphere
3	7.6%	Yeah, oh, get, yeah, well, know, yes, go, No, na, think, there, cos, gon, what, no, just, like, say
4	3.7%	player, win, game, Cup, season, club, team, play, match, goal, championship, score, League, ball
5	1.7%	aircraft, engine, railway, station, car, fly, train, pilot, squadron, locomotive, steam, line, crew
6	2.0%	patient, disease, treatment, study, cell, infection, gastric, health, acid, clinical, concentration, care
7	2.8%	God, Jesus, church, Christian, Christ, faith, king, bishop, prayer, gospel, spirit, pope, Holy
8	3.4%	school, award, teacher, student, education, pupil, course, curriculum, research, study, ref, subject
9	6.6%	okay, right, yeah, get, what, so, yes, if, just, well, go, think, know, actually, mean, there, oh
10	9.9%	government, Minister, party, political, election, Soviet, labour, state, country, president, Prime
11	4.1%	court, case, Act, law, defendant, plaintiff, contract, section, person, appeal, any, solicitor, under
12	4.9%	music, film, guitar, band, play, song, album, Eliot, bass, movie, sound, musical, pop, actor
13	3.5%	cell, gene, DNA, protein, energy, equation, sequence, molecule, temperature, surface, particle
14	6.5%	company, market, rate, price, share, cost, profit, tax, business, firm, UK, investment, bank
15	4.6%	Darlington, local, Council, council, housing, pension, councillor, authority, scheme, service, area
16	5.4%	art, painting, century, artist, exhibition, Edward, building, William, museum, town, king, church
17	5.5%	social, language, theory, word, may, text, behaviour, process, individual, information, meaning
18	15.5%	her, him, me, my, say, look, eye, smile, back, go, feel, door, tell, hand, know, think, like, could
19	5.6%	fish, water, your, plant, knit, bird, food, colour, breed, tank, can, horse, leaf, use, dry, egg, specie

0: W.non.ac.tech.engin; 1: W.news.script; 2: W.misc/W.app.science; 3: S.conv; 4: W.pop.lore/W.newsp.brdsh.t.nat.sports;
5: W.misc/W.leisure (texts for railway/aircraft enthusiasts); 6: W.ac.medicine; 7: W.religion; 8: W.misc/W.soc.science;
9: S.consult; 10: W.non.ac.polit.law.edu,W.newsp.brdsh.t.nat.reports; 11: W.ac.polit.law.edu; 12: W.newsp.brdsh.t.nat.arts,W.pop.lore;
13: W.non.ac.nat.science,W.ac.nat.science; 14: W.commerce; 15: S.meeting; 16: W.non.ac.humanities.arts,W.biography;
17: W.ac.soc.science; 18: W.fict.prose; 19: W.pop.lore,W.instructional/W.leisure

Fiction	door, smile, love, girl, herself, walk, moment, voice, himself, mind, watch, mother, remember
Polit1	political, labour, economic, national, European, union, million, Britain, trade, authority, Prime
<u>Health1</u>	care, parent, patient, hospital, health, mother, person, experience, doctor, body, baby, drug
Spoken	yeah, Right, okay, actually, hundred, pound, twenty, alright, sort, nice, thank, fifty, thirty, anyway
<u>Sports1</u>	game, player, team, season, match, England, goal, race, minute, score, championship, ball, League
<u>Biz1</u>	income, rate, payment, contract, pension, benefit, amount, scheme, account, value, loan, tenant
<u>Health2</u>	patient, cell, disease, acid, protein, gene, datum, concentration, value, occur, energy, method
Comp	user, software, computer, module, datum, file, Corp, application, Unix, database, version, product
News	police, yesterday, voice, studio, John, crime, officer, speaker, prison, council, murder, video-tape
<u>Spo2/Brit</u>	club, Road, Darlington, Ireland, Royal, hour, award, Hall, town, Sunday, School, Middlesbrough
<u>Travel</u>	fish, animal, plant, land, bird, road, tree, site, river, specie, mile, wind, rock, aircraft, forest, tank
<u>Biz2</u>	price, firm, share, bank, profit, product, investment, industry, sale, management, customer, rate
<u>History</u>	church, century, John, king, Christian, England, Roman, Jesus, death, himself, Edward, land
<u>Research</u>	award, research, process, organisation, analysis, subject, datum, worker, institution, type, model
Linguistics	language, theory, sense, example, class, human, individual, kind, experience, society, structure
Leisure1	music, film, artist, painting, exhibition, American, sound, picture, song, band, John, collection
Polit2	Minister, Soviet, president, military, election, March, force, National, party, announce, leader
Legal	court, order, person, section, legal, matter, defendant, appeal, authority, shall, plaintiff, decision
Edu	education, student, teacher, course, staff, training, authority, Council, community, pupil, management
Leisure2	colour, garden, hotel, plant, food, design, flower, wine, knit, hair, holiday, light, wall, restaurant

category is given after a slash. Obviously not all cluster members share the same code, but the pattern is consistent. The following is the distribution of the BNC genre codes of documents belonging to Cluster 18 in Table 2:

N	BNC codes	N	BNC codes
424	W.fict.prose	5	W.letters.personal
49	W.misc	5	S.brdcast.discussn
43	S.oral.history	4	W.religion
29	W.fict.poetry	4	W.non.ac.medicine
26	W.biography	4	S.speech.unscripted
19	W.non.ac.soc	4	S.classroom
5	W.pop.lore	3	W.non.ac.humanities
5	W.essay.school	3	W.newsp.brdsh.t.social

The documents outside of W.fict.prose are still reasonably similar, as they include ADG (a book for teenage

girls), ADM (accounts of travelling through Ireland), AP7 (experiences of old age), etc.³

The topics produced by the LDA package in R lack information about their relative size and consistency, so I gave them indicative labels on the basis of their keywords.

The two methods agreed on a number of domains, such as fiction, local British and international affairs. However, for some domains (underlined in Table 2) the clusters and topic models disagreed. One considerable difference stems from the ability of topic models to differentiate between the everyday language and professional discourse (the topics labelled as business and health care). In addition to this, hard clustering did not produce clusters related to history

³The ids are from the BNC index (Lee, 2001).

and research, which constitute relatively small (but consistent) topics in the BNC, e.g., documents HHY, HJO, HPN, etc, containing research project applications and texts on project management. Also, LDA generated a cluster combining references to sport clubs with other local British texts, possibly generalising on the membership of their keywords to place names in the UK.

3.2. Comparing Internet corpora to the BNC

The same procedure was applied to ukWac and generated the clusters and topics reported in Table 3. The clusters offer a quick way into comparing the composition of ukWac to that of the BNC. For instance, there is a cluster without specific keywords (Cluster 0 in ukWac). This closely corresponds to the fiction cluster in the BNC (Cluster 18 in Table 2). However, unlike the BNC the ukWac cluster contains little fiction and mostly consists of diary-like blogs, discussion forums on everyday topics and chats.

Domains that reasonably match both the BNC and ukWac include political news, sports, health, business and religion. The differences concern a broader collection of topics in ukWac within each domain, as well as the presence of more modern texts. Clustering of ukWac detects two clusters with keywords related to computing, one of which (Cluster 7) is quite similar to Cluster 0 in the BNC. Another computing cluster of ukWac (15) belongs to the field of web-based communications (the longer list of its keywords also includes *HTML*, *Internet*, *click*, *Google*, etc).

RB clustering in Cluto seems to be considerably more efficient on a large corpus than LDA. Clustering of the entire ukWac took 1494 sec, while LDA was not able to deal with a selection of more than 500,000 documents from ukWac (on a computer with 4GB memory), and producing topic models even for this subset took 4896 sec (clustering of the same subset with Cluto took 304 sec).

Even though the clusters and the topic models in Table 3 are drawn from two slightly distributions, there is a broad similarity between their results. The clusters of music, movies, health, computing, communication, food and gardening, religion, politics, travel and business have compatible keywords.

Table 4 lists the clusters generated for itWac, an Italian web-corpus collected using the same compilation procedure as ukWac. It again showed broad compatibility with the domains of pages in itWac, including film (Cluster 0), food (1), blogs and chats (2 and 7), legal texts (3,9), music (4), education (5 and 17), computers (6), religion (8), sports (10), health (11), politics (12 and 13), business (14), culture (15), communication (16), travel (18) and local news (19). Some differences between the keywords in itWac and ukWac are related to the realities in individual countries (*Berlusconi vs Labour*). In ukWac there is a Do-It-Yourself cluster (4) and a cluster on NHS (10), while itWac contains two legal clusters (3 and 9), their longer keyword lists reveal that Cluster 9 is more about criminal cases, while Cluster 3 is about more general legislation.

3.3. Comparing comparable corpora

Energy corpora differ from the BNC or ukWac in their size (less than 10 million words). It was also expected that

we can deal with fewer subdomains in them. The I_2 value was again not indicative, so the experiment was set for 15 clusters. As in the previous experiments both clustering and topic models were used. However, on a smaller corpus hard clustering produced less clearly interpretable results (also probably because of the difficulty in clear separation of relatively similar topics), while LDA produced fairly reasonable models listed in Table 5.

The analysis of topic models contradicted the original assessment made on the basis of term lists extracted from the corpora using the standard BootCat procedure (Baroni and Bernardini, 2004):⁴

7467 renewable energy	1508 возобновлять энергия
3127 greenhouse gas	1401 парниковый газ
3049 natural gas	2106 природный газ
2320 solar energy	2274 солнечный энергия
1994 carbon dioxide	1124 углекислый газ
1920 solar cell	2710 солнечный батарея
1529 fuel cell	862 топливный элемент

Given the overlap between the terms with similar frequencies and the fact that the corpora were collected with the set of keywords, it was expected that their content is sufficiently similar, and overall the corpora are good candidates for extracting and aligning term lists. However, LDA identified some topics present in both corpora, which are less ideal for term extraction, such as information for investors and news about utility companies, forums (we can expect less consistency in terminology used there) and legal texts. The Russian corpus was also contaminated with documents relating to computers (because of links to *power supply*), general news and student essays, which contain low-level introductions into a range of topics in this field. In general such lists of topics are useful in cleaning the corpus to achieve its greater consistency.

4. Conclusions

Three main outcomes of this study concern:

1. the possibility of rapid unsupervised assessment of the content of large corpora (clusters still need human interpretation, but this can be done quickly as long as they are consistent);
2. the possibility of comparing the content of corpora across languages without using any external resources, such as dictionaries;
3. the difference between hard clustering and LDA.

With respect to (1), we can use clustering to reveal more information even about a well-annotated corpus, such as the presence of a considerable cluster of texts for railway and aircraft enthusiasts in the BNC (otherwise obscurely coded as W.misc or W.leisure). It also shows broad classes of texts in a corpus of unknown composition such as ukWac or itWac.

With respect to (2), the clusters can be used to compare the content of individual corpora, but the interpretation needs to be done manually again. Intersection between the keywords of clusters in two corpora can be also done automatically.

⁴Lemmatisation of term elements in Russian affects the syntactic pattern of the composite term (Sharoff et al., 2008).

Table 3: Keywords clusters and topic models in ukWac

0	12.2%	I, her, he, she, my, his, me, him, i, it, do, say, PM, post, man, go, have, love, think, but
1	7.5%	road, mile, town, Canal, park, Road, walk, route, fn, Park, Street, Museum, village, north
2	2.5%	game, poker, player, ball, play, Sudoku, puzzle, sudoku, score, Games, win, goal, casino, match, tournament
3	4.6%	school, teacher, education, pupil, learn, skill, learning, child, student, training, teaching, learner
4	5.8%	water, cleared, colour, dive, light, surface, diver, valve, boat, wheel, wall, battery, bike, engine
5	10.0%	sector, organisation, local, business, development, management, sustainable, environmental
6	5.6%	student, University, module, research, study, course, academic, Studies, degree, science, graduate
7	6.3%	datum, system, software, model, use, computer, network, data, technology, user, NUN, solution
8	1.4%	insurance, mortgage, loan, property, Insurance, auto, quot, lender, rate, insurer, Agents
9	2.1%	God, Jesus, Christ, Christian, church, Lord, he, Church, Bible, his, sin, faith, prayer, verse, Him
10	3.1%	patient, care, NHS, health, nurse, hospital, clinical, nursing, mental, medical, service, Trust, Nursing
11	3.5%	plant, fish, bird, garden, flower, tree, food, specie, fruit, wine, seed, vegetable, cook, sauce, soil, sugar
12	3.1%	disease, drug, treatment, cancer, patient, cell, blood, infection, symptom, therapy, animal, gene, risk
13	3.2%	club, race, season, win, League, Cup, team, player, championship, match, lap, football, Championship
14	7.0%	pension, government, Committee, Labour, union, that, political, shall, Minister, vote, member
15	5.4%	file, search, user, text, server, use, Windows, web, page, site, library, directory, Web, browser
16	5.9%	customer, company, your, you, payment, business, sale, product, card, any, charge, market, service, price
17	3.5%	hotel, bedroom, room, holiday, beach, accommodation, apartment, restaurant, bathroom, cottage
18	4.8%	music, song, band, album, guitar, sound, musical, dance, vocal, gig, jazz, bass, track, play, concert
19	2.4%	film, movie, cinema, camera, DVD, comedy, actor, star, Jolen, scene, Hollywood, character
Music		music, song, game, player, band, album, club, season, sound, guitar, ball, score, match, goal, love
Movies		film, game, seem, never, something, quite, story, love, watch, race, turn, friend, movie, though
Health1		patient, care, treatment, drug, hospital, medical, doctor, clinical, woman, nurse, disease, mental
Comp		file, image, user, program, value, type, text, code, object, datum, function, display, click, version
History		John, William, Royal, James, history, David, George, King, Thomas, century, Robert, Peter, Hall
Goods		poker, wedding, game, price, artist, film, online, gift, wine, food, card, exhibition, colour, puzzle
Health2		cell, disease, protein, model, gene, effect, blood, datum, test, human, patient, food, cause, analysis
Garden		water, plant, animal, fish, tree, bird, specie, energy, garden, food, land, soil, farm, farmer, crop, waste, climate
Travel		room, hotel, walk, mile, road, town, house, bedroom, village, boat, holiday, garden, accommodation
Comm		Internet, software, user, customer, network, computer, technology, online, phone, server, mobile
Soc		social, language, political, history, human, society, theory, century, culture, word, text, idea, cultural, seem
Biz1		sector, market, organisation, industry, investment, million, management, financial, growth, cent, opportunity
Science		Research, library, resource, Institute, Centre, Science, publication, journal, Society, College, Department
Polit1		Iraq, Labour, political, attack, police, force, party, election, British, vote, military, weapon, Minister
Polit2		management, Committee, consultation, proposal, ensure, environmental, authority, safety, risk, review
Biz2		insurance, loan, payment, property, rate, mortgage, credit, claim, pension, income, employer, employee
Edu		skill, teacher, education, pupil, teaching, training, module, teach, learning, School, academic, language
Legal		shall, person, payment, court, request, party, apply, legal, notice, agreement, provision, liability, register
Local		Centre, Community, Road, meeting, West, council, volunteer, East, County, Trust, Borough, resident, District
Religion		Jesus, church, Christian, love, Christ, Lord, word, shall, faith, Bible, never, death, spirit, himself, heart

With respect to (3), clustering is a better approach to web-sized corpora, as LDA cannot reasonably handle ukWac and it takes considerably more time on the BNC or itWac. At the same time, on smaller corpora, LDA detects models which are easier to interpret in comparison to clustering solutions.

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Table 4: Keywords in clusters of itWac

0	2.59%	film, cinema, regista, attore, personaggio, regia, scena, cinematografico, protagonista, pellicola, cast, storia
1	1.07%	vino, olio, cucchiaino, uovo, burro, cuocere, pasta, piatto, latte, zucchero, formaggio, pepe, farina, cucina
2	11.53%	mio, mi, che, suo, non, essere, dire, avere, io, uomo, tuo, fare, lui, quello, ti, ma, occhio, cosa, amore
3	13.99%	articolo, numero, comma, decreto, legge, cui, previsto, lavoro, relativo, presente, servizio, lavoratore
4	2.37%	musica, disco, canzone, album, musicale, brano, band, concerto, rock, suonare, chitarra, musicista, cd
5	3.19%	scuola, scolastico, docente, insegnante, alunno, classe, formativo, didattico, formazione, istruzione, educativo
6	1.71%	file, server, Windows, utente, software, Microsoft, versione, programma, web, browser, utilizzare, Linux
7	7.39%	mi, ciao, io, non, messaggio, ti, mio, avere, fare, se, inviare, ma, me, scrivere, dire, sapere, cosa, tuo, Posted
8	3.86%	chiesa, Dio, Gesù, Cristo, cristiano, santo, papa, fede, suo, cattolico, vescovo, religioso, uomo, padre
9	6.79%	articolo, emendamento, commissione, legge, esame, numero, relatore, corte, sentenza, comma, giudice
10	4.27%	squadra, gioco, giocatore, gara, partita, giocare, atleta, campionato, calcio, vincere, gol, atletico, tifoso, sport
11	3.01%	paziente, malattia, cellula, medico, farmaco, terapia, clinico, medicina, tumore, patologia, salute, sanitario
12	5.87%	guerra, Iraq, americano, pace, Bush, contro, palestinese, militare, terrorismo, popolo, israeliano, iracheno
13	7.56%	politico, governo, partito, europeo, paese, presidente, politica, Berlusconi, parlamento, maggioranza, voto
14	3.91%	banca, euro, mercato, consumatore, milione, prezzo, aumento, miliardo, sindacato, paese, lavoratore, Cgil
15	3.89%	teatro, arte, mostra, artista, opera, libro, spettacolo, romanzo, poesia, museo, autore, storia, scena, artistico
16	3.20%	Internet, rete, utente, software, prodotto, tecnologia, sito, servizio, cliente, web, elettronico, azienda, digitale
17	6.67%	università, ricerca, scientifico, studio, corso, universitario, laurea, professore, scienza, concorso, biblioteca
18	3.14%	Hotel, mare, hotel, acqua, albergo, isola, zona, situare, vacanza, spiaggia, metro, antico, città, km, ristorante
19	3.96%	Provincia, assessore, comune, sindaco, provinciale, parco, regione, comunale, territorio, area, cittadino

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Table 5: Comparing English and Russian energy corpora

1	Table, Equipment, Market, Consumption, Capacity, Production, Industry, Generation, Distribution, Transformers, Sector
2	earth, atmosphere, dioxide, surface, cool, cause, warming, fluid, radiation, methane, reservoir, human, rock, warm
3	reactor, Nuclear, uranium, radioactive, barrel, mine, Uranium, fission, cent, Petroleum, reserve, billion, mining, safety
4	ocean, wave, OTEC, Ocean, tide, Intel, Tidal, Wave, marine, Hawaii, offshore, Conversion, device, surface, conversion
5	Commission, Public, shall, bill, Utility, credit, Federal, contract, FERC, eligible, District, regulation, federal, County
6	distribute, consumer, distribution, network, peak, meter, period, investment, value, datum, average, sector, reliability, factor
7	speed, rotor, blade, field, magnetic, shaft, circuit, wire, engine, transformer, phase, connect, rotate, frequency, torque
8	cogeneration, hydrogen, ethanol, engine, wood, combustion, Biomass, boiler, burn, crop, convert, landfill, residue, gasoline
9	Green, News, Hydro, Business, India, Stock, Development, Sustainable, Geothermal, Alternative, Environmental
10	river, hydroelectric, hydro, reservoir, fish, River, head, blade, hydroelectricity, Hydro, Hydropower, height, stream
11	post, read, bill, want, look, article, problem, money, green, really, question, link, warming, news, storey, idea, What, talk
12	announce, billion, Tags, investment, megawatt, Kansas, expect, sign, April, News, green, California, feed-in, release, Farm
13	sustainable, policy, economic, sector, reduction, Development, management, national, international, community
14	module, light, silicon, inverter, watt, sunlight, hour, roof, saving, device, appliance, save, film, array, tower, house, electron
15	Program, National, Department, California, Center, Association, Resources, Public, Information, Efficiency, Service, page
1	новость (news), ноутбук (laptop), процессор (processor), комментарий (comment), компьютер (computer), теле- фон (phone), ученый (scientist), рубрика (heading), память (memory), мобильный (mobile), intel, energy
2	финансовый (financial), государство (state), инвестиция (investment), мера (measures), доля (proportion), поли- тика (politics/strategy), правительство (government), национальный (national), потребность (demand)
3	ооо (Ltd), электронный (electronic), бесперебойный (uninterruptible), продажа (sale), дизельный (diesel), купить (buy), ремонт (repair), чертеж (drawing), ибп (UPS), фирма (firm), каталог (catalogue), товар (goods)
4	вот (this/yeah), кто (who), да (yes), сделать (do), сейчас (now), говорить (say), там (there), ни (neither), ли (would), надо (should), просто (simply), сам (-self), знать (know)
5	коммунальный (utilities), жилой (resident), федеральный (federal), водоснабжение (water supply), отопление (heating), оплата (payment), жкх (utilities), помещение (room), энергосбережение (energy saving)
6	рф (Russia), рао эс (Unified Energy System), подробно (details), инвестиционный (investment), директор (direc- tor), правительство (government), президент (president), глава (chairman), новость (news), январь (January)
7	конференция (conference), выставка (exhibition), устойчивый (sustainable), научный (scientific), наука (science), охрана (protection), энергосбережение (energy saving), энергоэффективность (energy efficiency)
8	геотермальный (geothermal), биомасса (biofuel), водород (hydrogen), отходы (waste), возобновляемый (renew- able), ветроэнергетика (wind generation), топливный (fuel), сжигание (burning), вэу (wind farm), солнце (sun)
9	море (sea), глобальный (global), океан (ocean), растение (plant), лес (forest), загрязнение (pollution), потепление (warming), природа (nature), парниковый (greenhouse), животное (animal), организм (organism), планета (planet)
10	плотина (dam), добыча (production), сооружение (installation), водохранилище (reservoir), месторождение (de- posit), запас (resource), очистка (purification), сырье (raw materials), сточный (sewage)
11	аккумулятор (battery), воздушный (air), насос (pump), емкость (capacity), нагрузка (load), рисунок (drawing), ротор (rotor), конструкция (design), вал (shaft), корпус (body), вращение (rotation), мм (mm), охлаждение (cool- ing)
12	тэц (CHP), энергосистема (grid), газотурбинный (gas turbine), когенерация (cogeneration), киловольт (kV), на- грузка (load), котельная (boiler station), генерация (generation), теплоснабжение (heating supply), выработка (production)
13	паровой (steam), котел (boiler), силовой (power), трансформатор (transformer), гост (GOST), частота (frequency), пар (steam), линия (line), power, преобразователь (converter), передача (transmission), реактивный (reactive), переменный (alternating), провод (wires)
14	русский (Russian), улица (street), война (war), язык (language), московский (Moscow), республика (republic), школа (school), век (century), ребенок (child), франция (France), текст (text), германия (Germany), игра (game), километр, книга, транспорт, история, культура,
15	реферат (essay), реактор (reactor), движение (movement), ядро (nucleus), наука (science), поле (field), атом (atom), реакция (reaction), нейтрон (neutron), физика (physics), планета (planet), магнитный (magnetic)